

IS THE “FITNESS PARTY” REALLY FUN FOR ALL?: AN EXAMINATION OF THE
GENDER NON-CONFORMING INDIVIDUALS EXPERIENCE IN ZUMBA

by

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Introduction

Zumba's fusion of dance and fitness has transformed the ways exercise can be enjoyed all across the world. Aimed to attract an extensive and diverse audience, Zumba has garnered the enjoyment of over 12 million people across 125 countries in various fitness centers and gyms (Zumba Fitness, n.d.). This group fitness format incorporates aerobic-style moves with Latin dance styles and rhythms to offer exercisers a new fitness space where they can "Ditch the Workout! Join the Party" (Zumba Fitness, n.d.). In particular, this unconventional fitness format has attracted the attention of many cisgender women. Much of this attraction is rooted in the plentitude of health benefits Zumba offers (Cugusi et al., 2019; Ljubojevic et al., 2014; Suri et al., 2017) and the deep-rooted magnetism cisgender women feel towards group fitness and dance classes (Markula, 2003). Zumba finds itself embedded in a long history of the feminization of group fitness, as the Zumba format has given cisgender women the opportunity to shape their bodies into the ideal standard of the feminine body. Effects of this history are still present, as group fitness classes, including Zumba, are more likely to become staples in cisgender women's fitness preferences than their cisgender man counterparts (Nieri & Hughes, 2016, 2021; Bianca de Menezes Nascimento & Cruz de Oliveria, 2020). Understanding where the popularity of Zumba stems from is based on a long history of scholarship that frequently centers on the cisgender woman's experience, with limited acknowledgment of individuals who identify outside the binary.

In recent years, the visibility of gender non-conforming individuals has increased in conversations regarding inclusivity and safety in the fitness space, bringing to the forefront issues with the binary foundation of the industry (Pattison et al., 2022). There are exponentially more barriers within the fitness industry toward gender non-conforming individuals'

participation than their cisgender peers, such as the lack of gender-neutral and gender-affirming facilities and activities, visible and verbal prejudice against queer and trans individuals, and internalized distress from being gender non-conforming in a space that is built on the foundation of the gender binary (Elling & d'Escury, 2017; Hargie et al., 2017; Pattison et al., 2022; Petterson, 2021; Storr et al., 2022). Zumba has been claimed to be a format that anyone can enjoy; however, its feminized foundation, which is intertwined with the sustainability of the gender binary, creates a complicated appeal to gender non-conforming individuals. Focusing on this population allows us to comprehend how the cultivation of Zumba's values is experienced from a more gender-expansive perspective.

Zumba's core values encourage community-forward and inclusivity-driven tactics to be at the forefront of each class. Therefore, this study aims to elucidate the experiences of community and authentic self-expression for gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba. Two primary questions guided this project: (1) How is community cultivated for gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba with the other participants and the instructor? and (2) How does the Zumba class environment allow gender non-conforming students to feel comfortable expressing their gender identity? To address these research questions, semi-structured interviews were utilized to explore significant influences that led to participants' participation in Zumba and how identifying as gender non-conforming played a part in how they participated in the class that had historically catered to the femininity cultivated by cisgender women. Informed by queer theory, this research uncovers the macro and micro politics that are operative when a gender non-conforming body makes space for themselves in a fundamentally binary industry. The voices of the participants are prominent throughout the study to illuminate the workings of different systems of power from a perspective traditionally obscured by dominant narratives.

This paper is structured into several vital sections, each presenting a significant purpose in comprehending the study's findings. Following this introduction, the literature review provides a comprehensive overview of the two bodies of literature in which this research intersects and highlights the limited pre-existing overlap between the research on the sociocultural effects of group fitness, specifically Zumba, and the experiences of gender non-conforming and transgender individuals in fitness and sport. The section on queer theory outlines the theoretical concepts and ideas that situate this study's approach to obtaining and interpreting the findings. The methodology details the strategies of recruitment, data collection, and the framework used to analyze the data. The analysis presents three distinct themes that contributed to shaping the experience for gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba. Finally, the conclusion summarizes the analyzed data, linking it back to the questions of community cultivation and comfortability of authentic expression and reiterating the significance of research in this population.

Literature Review

The world of fitness is a vast field where gender is constantly sculpted and reshaped. A significant amount of research around fitness spaces and culture has stayed within the boundaries of the binary genders: man and woman. Much less scholarship has focused on the experiences of people who do not fit within the binary, and therefore, research is needed within this space. This research project, which explores the experiences of gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba, will contribute to this understudied population. In so doing, it sits at the intersection of two bodies of literature. First, this study contributes to the body of literature that takes a socio-cultural perspective on gender in the fitness industry, focusing on gym and group fitness spaces. Secondly, it pulls from a body of literature that deconstructs the systematic challenges

and experiences of trans and gender non-conforming individuals in the broader context of physical activity and sport. By examining this existing research, this project aims to add literature that decreases the gap between the impact of group fitness and gender non-conforming individuals.

The Construction of Gender Through Fitness

The Gendered Fitness Space

The fitness craze in the 1970s and 1980s solidified the gender divide that normalized specific fitness formats for each gender category. As a result, feminist scholars became intrigued by the ways gender was being constructed in fitness spaces. Early scholarship focused on how fitness was used to segregate women into specific fitness spaces to uphold an idealized body standard (Dworkin, 2003; Markula, 2003). For example, Dworkin (2003) addresses the unequal use of cardiovascular and weight rooms by men and women. She illustrates how women often stayed in the cardiovascular room as it promoted the slim and toned body type that became the idealized version of femininity. As the cardiovascular rooms expanded and group fitness became more popular, scholars simultaneously noted levels of empowerment from women participating in these spaces (Dworkin, 2003; English, 2020; Markula, 2003). Markula (2003) points to fitness as a site of resistance for women as they could build a connection with their bodies that earlier patriarchal views of womanhood did not allow. Scholars like Dworkin (2003) and Markula (2003) highlight the contradictory nature of fitness for women as coexisting sites of the sustainability of the ideal feminine body and the reclamation of autonomy over one's body.

Specialized Group Fitness Formats

Research around fitness recently became more interested in looking into specialized fitness formats (e.g., CrossFit, Barre, LesMills) (Jones, 2023; Andreasson & Johansson, 2015).

Within this research, authors have pulled from previous scholarship (Dworkin, 2003; Coen et al., 2018) the perspective to look into the functions gender has in these specific spaces. In Jones' (2023) comparative analysis between CrossFit and Barre, the goal of each format was dictated by desired body types. With masculinity and femininity being closely tied to bulkiness and slenderness, respectively, the formats catered their emphasis on strength training (Crossfit) or aerobic type (Barre). Crossfit and Barre's demographic of students differs in part due to women's desire for the lean body that Barre motivates. Conversely, men are attracted to the muscularity that Crossfit emphasizes. While the binary gender divide is still present, current scholarship has pointed to the evolution of fitness format's views on the body. Andreasson and Johansson (2015) interviewed Les Mills founder Jackie Mills, where it was revealed that an application of a philosophy of the body that aims to understand the social context in which each participant is situated starts to push gender-neutral exercises. Andreasson and Johansson (2015) speak to how specific exercises used in group fitness classes were created out of societal expectations of body image rather than feedback from the participants. A format like Les Mills contests these practices to create a framework for a fitness class that "...helps people make good choices based on understanding" (Andreasson & Johansson, 2015, p. 40) rather than having students come in with predetermined results created by the organization. Therefore, taking on a philosophy that centers the participant leads to gender-neutral exercises that can be adapted to fit the image the participant wants to express. While gender non-conforming individuals were not explicitly mentioned, research has suggested a push to be more conscious of the construction of gender outside the binary.

Situating Zumba© Fitness

Importantly, for this research project, there has been some research that specifically looked at gender from a sociocultural perspective in the Zumba format. Within this scholarship, researchers have looked at the dominance of women in Zumba spaces (Bianca de Menezes Nascimento & Cruz de Oliveira, 2020; English, 2020; Nieri & Hughes, 2016), instructor's strategies to uphold Zumba's reputation of having a welcoming, party-like environment, (Nieri & Hughes, 2021), and the creation of community (Bianca de Menezes Nascimento & Cruz de Oliveira, 2020; English, 2020; Nieri & Hughes, 2016). Born out of resistance to Euro-centric forms of fitness, Zumba holds the values of community building and fun above body image and conformity between student and instructor (Nieri & Hughes, 2016, 2021; Bianca de Menezes Nascimento & Cruz de Oliveira, 2020). Nieri and Hughes (2021) note how Zumba instructors are trained to decenter themselves as the standard and focus on providing students with tools to move their bodies that align with their fitness journey and gender expression. Greater levels of comfort and engagement stem from the implementation of Zumba's core values, which result in significant community-building (Nieri & Hughes, 2016; Bianca de Menezes Nascimento & Cruz de Oliveira, 2020). However, Zumba's roots in dance have turned the format into a women-dominated space and are subject to the previous dichotomy of resistance and upholding patriarchal norms of fitness (Nieri & Hughes, 2016). Nieri and Hughes (2016) found that the Zumba participants valued the freedom of expression Zumba gave them; however, the expressions that women strived for were shaped by their idealized form of femininity. In this study, participants' initial motivations for attending Zumba were to lose weight and shape their bodies in ways not associated with a bulky and muscular frame. There was little indication of participants venturing into other fitness classes that paralleled masculinity or androgyny, with

greater attention given to building muscle. Given the nuances, scholars have emphasized the unique values that have made Zumba popular and different from other group fitness formats.

There is a considerable amount of research that explores the relationship between gender and fitness spaces. At the foundation of these fitness spaces is a structure that divides men and women while simultaneously creating an environment where people can feel connected and empowered in their bodies. In this scholarship about gender construction in fitness spaces, the focus on gender non-conforming identities is disproportionate to the binary identities, with little to no scholarship exploring this population's experiences in fitness spaces. This project will thus make a significant contribution to addressing the gap in the literature.

Gender Non-Conforming Individuals' Experience with Fitness

A significant amount of research stays within the scope of the gender binary, limiting the knowledge of the experiences of those who do not conform to such ideals. The experiences and perspectives of fitness that exist from gender non-conforming individuals that have been published have primarily focused on physical activity broadly, looking more towards experiences in sports, physical activity classes in childhood, and gym spaces (as opposed to the fitness studio). This scholarship has emphasized systemic exclusion, lack of safety, and the desire of gender non-conforming people to participate in various types of physical activity.

Systematic Exclusion

Many scholars have discussed how trans and nonbinary people feel excluded from sports and physical activity from a young age (Pattison et al., 2022; Hargie et al., 2017; Storr et al., 2017). Bell et al. (2023) discuss the ways exclusion is experienced and taught in early elementary years and is salient throughout future years. She uses the fitness industrial complex, which maintains a capitalist and patriarchal view on the standard of health and beauty, to discuss

how bodies that do not fit the ideal image, including gender non-conforming bodies, get excluded. Bell et al.'s (2023) research shows how these standards have been implemented in elementary physical education classes, as they were critical sites of early experiences of cis-heterosexism from peers and teachers. Alongside such scholarship, many have emphasized the heightened enforcement of hegemonic masculinity through team sports activities and outcasting those who did not participate in respective activities (Pattison et al., 2022; Hargie et al., 2017; Storr et al., 2017). Hargie et al. (2017) elaborate on how early interactions with cis-heterosexism builds upon the minority stress model for those in the queer and trans community cultivating fear and aversion to other kinds of fitness spaces. Fitness and sport have a significant capacity to strengthen interpersonal relationships and offer opportunities to foster fitness-related skills, such as self-discipline and confidence to face loss and rejection (Hargie et al., 2017). However, the functional and relational exclusion toward gender non-conforming individuals in the fitness space due to the lack of gender-neutral and affirming facilitates and strategies of coaching restricts the fitness benefits that Hargie et al. (2017) put forth.

Lack of Inclusivity and Safety in Fitness Spaces

Another central theme within the literature around gender non-conforming people's experiences is the physical barriers for gender non-conforming individuals that limit safety and motivation. A significant portion of the research highlights the lack of services in fitness spaces, like gender-neutral restrooms and changing rooms, or training on how to address gender-based discrimination (Pattinson et al., 2022; Hargie et al., 2017; Petterson, 2021). A common discussion was around the fact that without gender-neutral facilities or trainings to aid in the diminishment of hegemonic masculinity salient in fitness spaces, the engagement of gender-non-conforming individuals is significantly lower than their peers (Pattinson et al., 2022;

Petterson, 2021). As previous research stated, fitness spaces are founded on creating division amongst the binary genders, furthering the lack of space and visibility for gender non-conforming identities in fitness spaces.

The Need and Desire to Participate

The final theme within this scholarship focused on the significant need and desire of gender non-conforming individuals to be a part of the fitness culture. Consistent exercise and activity are linked to better physical health, mental health, body image, and worth perceptions. However, the majority of research concludes that gender non-conforming individuals are less likely to participate in physical activity and have more negative results regarding physical and mental health and feelings of self-worth (Pattinson et al., 2022; Storr et al., 2017; Muchicko et al., 2014).

Scholars have noted the community aspect that comes with fitness spaces and sports. These communities provide peer social support and care, which can tremendously affect one's well-being (Elling & Collot d'Escury, 2017). There are a limited number of reports highlighting the community gender non-conforming individuals have found in sports teams and gym spaces. It has been concluded through this literature that a significant portion of gender non-conforming do not have as easy access to an affirming community in fitness and sports but have the desire to find one (Elling & Collot d'Escury, 2017; Storr et al., 2017; Muchicko et al., 2014). Limited research has pointed to the most effective strategies to ensure a safe and affirming community for gender non-conforming individuals in fitness spaces. However, in order, for such a community to be created, research participants and members from the queer community suggest that changes need to be made in the fitness industry. Such suggestions have included gender-neutral facilities, increasing critical social consciousness in fitness classes, more gender non-conforming trainers

and instructors, and spaces to work through gender dysmorphia (Pattinson et al., 2022; Nieri & Hughes, 2021; Bell et al., 2023; Petterson, 2021).

The fitness industry is a site of significant influence and repetition of social gender norms. In the context of this project, fitness' influence on gender and the perspectives of fitness from gender non-conforming individuals will be brought together. There is a considerable gap in the literature at the intersection of these two bodies of literature. By understanding the gendered foundation of fitness spaces and the aversion gender non-conforming individuals have to fitness spaces, this research illuminates the persistence of the gendered history and sustainability in the fitness industry and the experiences of the gender non-conforming community in this domain.

Theoretical Framework

This research is situated within the framework of queer theory, a critical perspective that emerged in the late 20th century to deconstruct normative assumptions about sex, gender, gender expression, and sexuality (Browne & Nash, 2016). The term “queer theory” was coined in 1991, by Teresa de Lauretis, in her essay *Queer Theory: Lesbian and Gay Sexualities*. In this essay, de Lauretis emphasizes the need for a more nuanced and expansive understanding of sexuality and gender by refusing the normative white, cisgender, heterosexuality standards that ground sexual formations. In addition to the work of de Lauretis, many other theorists, such as Butler (1990), Sedgwick (1990), Rubin (1984), and Halberstam (1998), made early significant contributions to how queer theory is used and understood today.

Despite not explicitly being a queer theorist, much of what queer theory stems from are the concepts offered by Michel Foucault. In his 1976 book, *The History of Sexuality*, he critiques the normalcy of essentialism, which, according to Foucault, is the inherently fixed categorization of identity, resulting in universal assumptions about each identity group. His critique discusses

how fluidity in sexual expression continues to be regulated by powers that push heteronormativity into every aspect of society. Using Foucault's work has allowed many queer theorists to expose the systems that continue to perpetuate essentialist (and binary) forms of thinking.

As a practice, queer theory is a deconstructivist political project aimed at revealing the continuous effects of heteronormativity and the gender binary. Gender, as commonly understood, was confined to the constructs of femininity and masculinity and was fixed to one's biological makeup (Butler, 1990; Sedgwick, 1990). Gender has become fixed and isolated within the idea of identity. As a response, queer theorists argue that this positivist way of thinking was upholding a patriarchal society that pressured individuals to conform to the gender binary regardless of their internal feelings about gender. Scholars posed the concepts of gender performativity, multiplicity, and affect to push back against structures that repeat messages of cis-heteronormativity (Ahmed, 2004, 2006; Butler, 1990; Connell, 1987, 1993; Fausto-Sterling, 2000, 2012; Halberstam, 1998, 2005; Hooks, 1981; Rubin, 1984). Queer theory points to the multiple ways gender is constructed through other parts of one's identity and the emotional perspective that shapes one's interactions with society to allude to how gender is a more fluid experience that is contingent on more than biology (Ahmed, 2004, 2006; Halberstam, 2011, 2012; Sedgwick, 2003). Further, it is argued that gender is produced, not inherent, and is not tied to a fixed identity but rather a set of repetitive actions performed in social contexts (Butler, 1990; Halberstam, 1998; Sedgwick, 1990). Through these reconstructions of what gender means, queer theorists can reimagine a society in which queer and transgender individuals are liberated from the confines of cisheteronormativity and the gender binary.

Such ideas within queer theory guide this project. In particular, the project explores the binary nature of gender and sexuality that is promoted within Zumba and gym culture. Coming out of the group fitness craze in the 1980s, Zumba became women-dominated and sat in opposition to the traditional masculine spaces in fitness. The creation of group fitness, and by extension Zumba, is grounded in values that women perform specific exercises to maintain femininity while men perform other activities that support masculinity (Dworkin, 2003). Even as Zumba moves to be more gender-inclusive, aspects of the gender divide persist through the intimidation a masculine presence can create when engaging in dance moves that are considered “sexy” in a Zumba class for feminine bodies (Nieri & Hughes, 2016).

It is emphasized within queer theory that every aspect of society is gendered. Focusing on the gender non-conforming community within a system heavily situated on the formations of men and women sheds light on the current foundation of the fitness industry, sustaining exclusionary practices for those who do not identify within the binary. Therefore, utilizing queer theory will guide this project to identify the conditions in which marginalization and inclusion are experienced for gender non-conforming individuals in the Zumba space.

Positionality

The primary researcher on this project comes from a background in Women and Gender Studies, with experiences working in the LGBT Queer Resource Center at California State University, Fullerton, and as a certified Zumba instructor. As a bi-racial (settler white and Filipino), queer, cis-woman who is admittedly navigating her own gender identity, working in these spaces has shaped the perspectives and choices made during data collection and analysis. Being educated and socialized in America has required unlearning and decolonizing her mindset towards cisheteronormative expectations to gain an understanding of her own identity as well as

the greater gender non-conforming community. Additionally, her Southern California education informed her of the significance of using qualitative data when researching marginalized communities, as they often are subject to misrepresentation. Therefore, in many ways, the lead researcher has insider status as someone familiar with Zumba and has access to resources and knowledge pertaining to the format. Simultaneously, she is considered an outsider as her racial identity, location of socialization and education, and interpretation of her own gender identity differed from the participants. This status as both an insider and outsider affected the types of questions the participants were asked and the discussions that followed.

Throughout her academic and professional career, she has subscribed to epistemology theorized by queer and trans scholars. Queer epistemology assumes the social construction and performativity of gender that is institutionalized in industries such as fitness and wellness (Butler, 1990; Dworkin, 2003). The application of queer theory in the researcher's work has formed the lens through which she views the fitness industry. Viewing the fitness industry through this perspective contributed to her seeing the ways cisheteronormative standards of gender are capitalized on, which pointed her to the gap in the literature that focuses on gender non-conforming individuals.

The author would like to acknowledge directly her ability and privilege to navigate academia as an institution that contributes to the sustainability of oppressive systems that reproduce social, political, and economic barriers to the gender non-conforming community.

Methods

This study focuses on the lived experiences of gender non-conforming individuals through the use of queer theory. As discussed, queer theory in research focuses on centralizing the voices of individuals as their insight on systems of power uncover strategies of oppression

that often get overlooked by dominant narratives. Therefore, throughout the research process, the goals and intent are reflected through the methods as the participants’ voices guided the data, as they had the autonomy to speak to any story they deem significant. This section will outline the design used to collect and analyze the data.

Recruitment

Participants were recruited for this study based on self-identification with three essential criteria. Individuals were required to be at least 18 years of age, self-identified as gender non-conforming or with an adjacent label (non-binary, genderqueer, genderfluid, bigender, agender, transmasculine, transfemme, etc.), and participated in at least one Zumba class. Recruitment occurred via various pathways, including emailing multiple LGBTQ+ resource centers, university fitness centers, and affinity housing groups. The researcher also utilized her Zumba network of students and instructors through promotion in classes and various social media platforms.

Data Collection

Overall, there were six participants, ranging from age nineteen to twenty-six. The gender identities and expressions varied across the six participants, each uniquely describing the ways they experience gender. There was also an assorted range of time spent participating in Zumba, as some participants considered themselves frequenters while others claimed to be inconsistent or new to their Zumba journey. See Table 1 for the list of participants.

Table 1

Pseudonym	Age	Self-Identification of Gender Identity and Expression	Number of Zumba classes
Riley	21	(non-binary) tendency to lean toward masculine expression; heavily linked to lesbian identity	Once a week for three months; new to Zumba
Jordan	19	(non-binary) tendency to lean toward	Couple times a year

		masculine expression; during a period before identifying as a trans-man	for a year (age 14); not a current participant
Avery	25	(agender) tendency to lean toward femininity expression; their femininity was not affected when they started identifying as agender	Once a week for two and a half years; current participant
Parker	23	(no strong relationship with labels, but if needed, then genderqueer) balance of femininity and androgyny; they perceive their gender identity based on how others perceive them	A couple of times in their youth, approximately seven times in their 20s (year break between the first two classes and the last five classes); not a current participant
Morgan	23	(nonbinary, trans-masc) tendency to lean toward masculine expression; maintains a level of “softness” that subverts ideas of hegemonic masculinity	Inconsistently for a year and a half; not a current consistent participant
Taylor	26	(dual-spirit*) tends to lean toward masculine and androgynous expressions; engage with femininity if the situation calls upon it or for safety precautions	Consistently throughout junior and senior years of high school (break until entered college); currently participate once or twice a week

*dual-spirit: identity exclusive to indigenous Native Americans who embody and/or hold masculine and feminine spirits within them

Participants partook in semi-structured interviews lasting between 30-60 minutes in the space of the participant’s choosing (physical or virtual). Allowing the participant to choose the time and location helped to deconstruct the strict binary of researcher and researched. It enabled participants to have a sense of autonomy and agency by selecting a location/medium where they felt comfortable and where they had a level of control over the conversation. The semi-structured interviews allowed for specific themes to be touched upon (interactions with the class

community and the tactics in which inclusion was cultivated) across all the interviews but allowed for flexibility within each interview. This flexibility allowed participants to speak upon topics they deemed significant in their experiences in Zumba classes. Giving the participants flexibility with the questions enabled them to control how much they wanted to share and allowed them to speak through the nuances of their experience. Interview questions focused on understanding participants' racial, class, and gender identities and their sexual orientations and breaking down their first Zumba class and their decision to stop or continue. To deconstruct participants' experiences in Zumba, the questions emphasized a curiosity about how community was built in the class and whether or not the class brought upon feelings of dysmorphia or euphoria for participants' gender identity (see Appendix A for the interview guide).

The audio recordings from the interview were transcribed for data analysis. Participants were emailed a copy of the transcription and had two weeks to make edits and add any additional content.

Data Analysis

Once the interviews were completed and transcribed, data was analyzed through the framework of thematic analysis. According to Braun and Clarke (2017), thematic analysis is “a method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns (themes) within data.” (pg. 297). This framework includes recursive steps, including familiarization, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, and defining and naming themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2017). The researcher immersed herself in the data while transcribing and re-reading the interviews. The researcher then completed the second step of generating initial codes, which were understood as details in the data that could potentially be associated with the two primary research questions. From there, parallels in the initial codes were examined to create themes that underpin a

centralizing concept. These themes were reviewed to determine the accuracy between the theme and raw data. Once the themes were finalized, the researcher could name and give descriptions that captured the essence of the data points. In total, three distinct themes were found across the data. Thematic analysis offers flexibility in approaching questions inductively or deductively (Braun & Clarke, 2012). This study combined the two as coding occurred within the data presented by the participants' experiences, but concepts from queer theory, such as cisheteronormativity and gender performativity, guided the analysis.

Analysis

After reviewing the six semi-structured interviews, gender non-conforming individuals' experiences in Zumba are highly nuanced and rely on the class's multiple elements. By utilizing the Braun and Clarke thematic analysis framework, three significant impacts arose that influenced how the participants interacted with the class community and found comfort in expressing their authentic gender identity. Regardless of whether or not a participant had a positive or negative experience, the inherent gender bias in the class, the amount of queer visibility, and the choices that instructors made contributed to the type of relationship the participants had with Zumba.

Inherent Gender Bias

For decades, group fitness space has expanded on a foundation targeting more feminine audiences. Zumba has not been exempt from this inherent gender bias, as femininity takes up a significant portion of the class environment through participant demographics, songs, dance moves, etc. (Nieri & Hughes, 2016; English, 2020). These elements that uphold the gender bias and binary reinforce a type of cisheteronormative femininity that creates a heightened sense of awareness and a prolonged “easing in” period for gender non-conforming participants as their

relationship with femininity did not align with what is being normalized and performed throughout the Zumba space.

Participants experienced overwhelming feelings of intimidation when walking into a room of all women or feminine-identified people. The type of femininity that is being exhibited to the participants was recognized as progressive as they saw a variety of body types, races, and ages. However, there was a lack of gender diversity or a deviation from traditional hyper-femininity. Initial participant observations focused on the difference in attire between themselves and everyone else in the class, the body parts accentuated during the dances, and the lyrics sung in the songs. Becoming hyperaware of these aspects of the class resulted in many participants experiencing gender dysphoric feelings. Gender dysphoria is not a uniform experience but can be articulated as the distress attributed to the misalignment of internal and external perceptions of one's gender identity and expression (Davy & Toze, 2018). For participant Riley, when discussing their first time walking into the Zumba class, they observed the differences between their expression of femininity and the standard of femininity that the class appeared to cultivate. Riley stated, "I was getting more in my head than I thought I would because I was like... oh, I kind of do not feel like a girl right now." The disconnection one feels between their internal and external perceptions of their gender, or gender dysphoria, was a heightened sensation for participants when initially entering the space. Being in this kind of environment served as a reminder for participants that their gender presentation did not align with the hegemonic femininity that dominated the Zumba classes. Embodying a type of femininity that incorporates elements of masculinity or androgyny or not expressing femininity at all exacerbated feelings of estrangement for many of the participants.

Gender dysphoria presents an additional challenge amidst the already uneasy process of navigating a novel environment. It is common for people to experience anxiety when trying something new, and those feelings are no different for gender non-conforming individuals. However, their anxiety was exacerbated and prolonged in the Zumba space as their relationship with femininity and the ways they expressed their gender diverged from what participants perceived as the standard of femininity present in the space. Depending on conditions relating to the structure of the class and their personal relationship with their gender identity, the intensity of feelings of gender dysphoria would fluctuate but never appear to go away, staying present for much of the Zumba class. In Taylor's reflection on their feelings of gender dysphoria in the Zumba space, they stated, "On a higher confidence day, yes [I was comfortable expressing myself.] When I'm not feeling so good in my skin, then not so much, it's [looks more like] trying to conform with the others so I don't look like an outcast or I don't look different." The institutional gender bias instigates internalized desires to conform, making solidifying comfortability in the Zumba space more complex. Conforming to the standard of the space went against participants' authentic gender identity, causing inner turmoil from trying to decipher whether adhering to norms to seem like an outcast or embodying their true self would make the class more manageable. Participants stated they did not have many examples of how to display agency over their movement as most of the class aligned with the hegemonic forms of femininity. Therefore, participants did not feel empowered to explore movement motivated by their true gender identity. In Morgan's reflection on their initial evaluation of their feelings during the class, they asked themselves, "...how do I take ownership of this movement without feeling entirely dysphoric in the way I move?" For participants, easing into the movements took

longer, as gender dysphoria and navigating comfortability were an additional mental hurdle that needed to be worked through.

Interestingly, participants did emphasize that the Zumba community was a very welcoming and friendly environment where there did not appear to be a conscious effort to uphold a standard of femininity; instead, participants felt the normative hyper-femininity that pervades the space. At its core, Zumba values diversity and inclusion and encourages its instructors and participants to hold and practice those values during class. Participants claimed to feel that openness but simultaneously felt the unconscious creation of a hegemonic feminine space that persists from decades of feminizing group fitness. The inner turmoil and fluctuating internal comfort sustain themselves in the gender bias, relying on peripheral conditions to be in place to remedy the uneasiness.

Overall, the inherent femininity that underlines the Zumba space is one of the first observations gender non-conforming individuals make upon entering the class. The mental repercussions of the hegemonic femininity made it difficult for participants to find the confidence to engage in the social aspects that are widely enjoyed by other Zumba participants (Nieri & Hughes, 2016). Implicit gender bias is a significant factor in gender non-conforming participants contemplating the decision of whether or not they should participate, which can have adverse effects on Zumba's values of inclusivity.

Instructor Choices

The instructor is critical in the cultivation of the class environment. Due to the repetitive structure of Zumba, there comes a point when students start to rely less on the instructor for instructing movement. However, participants felt as though the instructor played an integral role in demonstrating the class expectations and standards of behavior. As stated by Avery, "... the

instructor sets the tone, creates the environment, and sets unspoken expectations.” The instructor is a consistent factor in the class that students can expect to see and, therefore, is a new student’s first impression of the environment and functioning of the class. The main features of the class—song choice, dance choice, engagement, and energy—were all curated by the instructor and were highly influential on the comfort level of gender non-conforming students. Participants reported different approaches to these instructor choices, which can be categorized into approaches that were encouraging and approaches that were discouraging.

Numerous characteristics contributed to an uplifting environment orchestrated by the instructor. First and most salient was having an instructor who made unconditional efforts to interact with every person who participated in the class, whether through small gestures like high fives, dancing next to them during class, or through small talk before or after class. For the gender non-conforming students, the interactions that the instructor initiated eased fears of favoritism or bias toward other students who presented more in alignment with the norm of femininity. The fun that the instructors demonstrated when engaging with each student and the community as a whole was contagious for participants, and it acclimated them to the idea that they could also let go of their anxieties and have fun. Jordan spoke about how he could explore the fun aspects of the class because “[the instructor] would be cheering people on, clapping with them, dancing with them, and I thought it was just so cool to see... I was nervous before, but then, seeing how everyone else was having fun, I was just like this is cool. I could get down with this.” Emotionally discerning the instructor’s desire to connect with each student was pivotal in feeling empowered to engage with the community, even with high fives or small talk. Initially, connecting with the instructor gave participants an opportunity to vet the students’ demeanor, as they felt like the students reflected values similar to those of the instructor.

Additionally, participants commented on a pattern they noticed with instructors encouraging students to be creative and promoting Zumba's value of "adding your own flava." Participants described these instructors as ones who were not afraid to demonstrate different variations when it came to gendered dance expression and had fun while doing it. Riley stated, "I liked the way they incorporated both masculine and feminine songs and movements because it kind of pushed everyone in the room to experiment." Other instructors like Avery's would "[do] a little spiel about not doing what they were doing. You could do whatever you wanted." Participants who had instructors encourage this type of creativity felt empowered to find movement that gave them gender euphoria. When Riley spoke about their experience of having an instructor who encouraged and implemented gender fluidity in the dances, they stated, "...it pushed everyone in the room to experiment... and I liked being able to touch both sides of my energy when the stakes aren't that high, and at the end of the day, there's no pressure." These participants were able to mitigate previous feelings of intimidation from the pre-determined notion that the Zumba space was overtly feminine. They found comfort in being shown that it was a space of exploration and that their gender identity could be expressed through movement.

However, not all instructors held the same standard of how they viewed the social aspects of the Zumba fitness space. There was a reoccurring observation with some instructors where participants felt as though the instructors saw the class as nothing more than a space to work out and did not give enough attention to community aspects the space intrinsically creates. In Avery's reflection of an unwelcoming experience, they stated, "...they do have things in place to be accepting, but sometimes the people cultivate an energy that doesn't feel too inviting or too safe." Given the heightened feelings of gender dysphoria for gender non-conforming students, these instructors did not take the time to add things to the class to promote creative autonomy

and emphasized uniformity in the context of dance style and expression. Reflecting on a negative experience with a Zumba instructor, Morgan stated, “I don’t know if these instructors would understand the math that would be going on in my mind...or have the awareness to be inclusive.” Without taking the time to address the common mental hurdles students may be experiencing when entering the space, gender non-conforming participants were highly uncertain that the awareness of gendered obstacles was considered. It was accentuated that participants did not feel as though it was entirely the instructors’ fault or that there was malicious intent. The feelings of restriction and exclusion in these Zumba spaces paralleled the experiences of marginalization in other fitness spaces. Alluding to the binary foundation of fitness spaces, these reflections highlight how gender-expansive thinking remains irregular amongst fitness instructors.

Queer Visibility

Being able to see oneself represented in the Zumba space carries significant importance for gender non-conforming participants. There is a disparity in queer and gender non-conforming representation in the fitness industry, including Zumba and its marketing. Finding a way to add queerness to the class was integral for participants. Each participant, in turn, brought along a queer-identifying friend to their first session. Furthermore, many sought out instructors or sessions led by fellow queer individuals or those visibly supportive of the LGBTQ+ community, both in class and on social media.

Companionship is linked to increased social integration, a sense of belonging, and reduced anxiety and depression (Rook, 1987; Naidoo et al., 2022). Participants’ experiences paralleled this research with the caveat that the companion also identifies as queer. Non-queer companionship satisfied the need of physically having someone, but when needing to work

through the emotional and mental hurdles, non-queer companionship was insufficient in upholding adequate support to work through those obstacles, such as gender dysphoria. While experiencing discomfort during a class stemming from gender dysphoria, Parker spoke about the paradox of feeling supported physically by their non-queer friends but simultaneously isolated from their friends' inability to relate to what they were experiencing, "...I was with friends, so it wasn't like I was fully by myself, but it felt as though I was alone in that experience." However, when queer friends were present, participants expressed having a mutual understanding with their queer peers about the feelings of isolation and navigating the complexities of being queer and gender non-conforming in the Zumba space. As expressed in previous literature, gender non-conforming individuals do desire participation in a fitness community (Elling & Collot d'Escury, 2017; Storr et al., 2017; Muchicko et al., 2014), and bringing in a companion that was also queer increased social interactions with the greater class community amongst participants. Parker's first class back to Zumba, after experiencing significant discomfort with their body from previous Zumba classes, was with a queer and gender non-conforming friend. They stated, "...me and my friend made it really fun for ourselves in the back, and it was really comforting because I knew he, we don't identify similarly, but we do fall under that umbrella of gender queerness." All participants shared similar sentiments, and as a result, they felt more comfortable clapping, dancing, and cheering with the people next to them they did not know when they had a queer companion. The non-verbal communication between queer friends served as a gateway to feeling connected to the Zumba class and progressed into verbal small talk with other participants in the room.

Along with bringing a companion, the identity of the instructor or their level of allyship to the LGBTQ+ community played a significant role in the participants' engagement with the

class and the role of queer visibility. In Southern California, there is an abundance of Zumba classes offered at commercial gyms, college campuses, dance studios, etc., and a majority of instructors use social media to promote their classes. The ample amount of resources allowed participants to find an instructor who reflected an atmosphere with which they felt comfortable. Many participants were able to find instructors who were open about their queer identities, which was significant for participants when deciding whether or not they should continue with the instructor or with the format as a whole. Jordan's experience with their instructor was pivotal to his retention in the class, "...when I found out [my instructor] was gay, it made me feel more comfortable because I was like, now I know that she is totally chill with [my transness]." Similarly to having a queer companion present in the class, having an openly queer instructor elevated the experience as the participants expressed a level of trust and safety in the space. In classes with queer instructors, participants were more comfortable taking up space to express their authentic selves, as they sensed their authentic selves would be well received and encouraged. Additionally, the class atmosphere felt more prideful, and the student-initiated interactions increased, as participants presumed that the students in the class held supportive and accepting views of the LGBTQ+ community.

In summary, this analysis of the experiences of gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba pointed to three significant influencers. For gender non-conforming individuals, coming to Zumba requires mental and emotional preparation to alleviate the distress from gender dysphoria caused by the inherent abundance of hegemonic feminine energy present in Zumba (and gym spaces more broadly). Participants' experiences were further molded by the mindfulness of instructors having to put the idea of gender inclusivity into action, whether through the music they played or how they interacted with each student. This also extended to

how visible queerness was within the class, as participants' comfortability was partially shaped by their ability to relate to an aspect of the class that was or was associated with queerness. Participants shared that, to some extent, their desire for community and comfort in expressing their gender identity through dance was satisfied, given the conditions. However, they believed more could be institutionalized to ensure gender inclusivity is constant regardless of the class format.

Conclusion

This study has provided perspectives on how gender non-conforming individuals experience Zumba. Fitness for people who identify outside of the gender binary is primarily shaped by the obstacles created by the preservation of the gender binary present across the fitness industry. Aversion to fitness spaces, like Zumba classes, builds from macro and micro levels of exclusions, ranging from direct verbal disregard to the lack of resources and accommodations for various gender expressions. The Zumba space is not immune from these systematic prejudices, as the format tends to reinforce dominant feminine norms, following the trends that link the group fitness space to femininity and womanhood. Current literature primarily focuses on women's experiences in Zumba, highlighting the enjoyment rooted in the party-like atmosphere that brings students together in a low-stakes fitness environment. Zumba's core value of being fun-focused contributed to the significant community building and heightened levels of confidence women-identified students experienced when participating in Zumba. Yet, gender non-conforming individuals are given little acknowledgment within this scholarship, thus creating the grounds for this study.

Through semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis, this study focused on emphasizing the experiences of gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba. As

community-building and engaging in a low-stakes fitness environment were prominent themes in the current Zumba and group fitness literature, this research aimed to uncover these occurrences with gender non-conforming individuals. Specifically, this research was guided by the attempt to explore the following questions: (1) How is community cultivated for gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba with the other participants and the instructor? and (2) How does the Zumba class environment allow gender non-conforming students to feel comfortable expressing their gender identity?

Exploring the experiences of how gender non-conforming individuals navigated interacting with the Zumba community illuminated the interconnectedness of gender bias, the instructor's choices, and the level of queer visibility. The cultivation of community for gender non-conforming in Zumba is molded through the implicit gender bias that underlines the Zumba class and how the people in the class conform or push against it. For the participants, more time had to be taken to build up the confidence to engage with the Zumba community due to the overwhelming exhibit of femininity. On the micro level, that confidence to engage with the community was either deterred or stimulated by the energy the instructor exuded in class, as an instructor with unconditional enthusiasm and openness encouraged participants to be more engaged with the other students. Additionally, a class that exhibited a relatively significant amount of queerness reflected a standard of allyship that aided in gender non-conforming participants' comfortability in interacting with the community.

Gender non-conforming participants' comfortability in expressing their gender identity authentically was contingent on the same themes. Due to the gender dysphoria that was activated in the Zumba space, for many participants, their ability to find comfort in their bodies was constrained, making it difficult to be themselves in class. Given this basis of discomfort,

participants' comfort in expressing themselves was either encouraged or discouraged by the instructor and the way the instructor managed the class. Having a conscientious understanding of the engrained obstacles at the foundation of the Zumba space allowed instructors to create opportunities for participants to feel safe being themselves, as they felt their identities were considered and accepted. Comfortability was also heightened when queerness was visible in the class, as not only was there a sense of a standard of allyship but a simultaneous sense of relatability, which eased the fears that stemmed from feeling isolated as the only queer or gender non-conforming student.

Community building and comfortability in one's gender expression are enriched for gender non-conforming students when these conditions are in place. However, it is crucial to caution that a definitive conclusion on whether Zumba can be universally accepted as an inclusive space cannot be formulated. While many participants spoke highly of the Zumba space, faults and uncertainties still prolong the duration of comfortability interacting with the community and taking full ownership of their gender identity.

This study alludes to the intersection of impediments that gender non-conforming individuals face when in Zumba. On the one hand, participants had to face the social anxiety that comes from being in an unknown space that is principally feminine while simultaneously confronting the gender dysphoria that stems from moving the body in ways it possibly has not explored. The Zumba space provides an example of how peripheral measures, such as the social and material choices made by the instructor, are used to remedy the unsolved issue of the gender bias that continues to sustain an exclusionary gender binary throughout the fitness industry. However, in comprehending the manifestations of the instructor's choices and queer visibility in a binary-grounded format, future research and fitness policies have grounds to implement more

gender-expansive features to maximize the benefits of fitness spaces. From this research, it was highlighted how simple inclusive practices such as instructors giving everyone a high five or increasing the amount of queer representation in class have a significant impact on expanding the boundaries of who feels included in the Zumba space. Accentuated in the experiences of the participants, practical tactics were shared that promoted inclusivity and fun in the context of gender neutrality and affirmation. The underlying systematic issue of gender bias must not be forgotten in the promotion of gender-affirming fitness space, as through this research, it was shown that the inherent gender bias never disappeared even when all other conditions promoted inclusivity. The flexible structure of Zumba gives an opportunity to investigate different approaches to gender inclusivity and to subvert gendered expectations that are predetermined in the group fitness space. Gender non-conforming individuals are amongst the top communities that desire and lack a place in fitness, and their voices are the premise for the push towards a more gender-conscious fitness industry.

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Appendix A

This appendix consists of the interview guide used during interviews. These questions guided the interview and opened up opportunities for other related questions to be answered during the interview.

Interview Guide

Introduction

Thank you so much for agreeing to be part of this research project and taking the time to meet with me. This project will be led by me (Lauryn Jarvis) with ethical approval granted from the IRB at California State University, Fullerton. This project aims to understand the experiences of gender non-conforming individuals in Zumba classes by focusing on how you interacted with the community of students and the instructors and what factors made you stay or leave the format. You are being asked to participate in this study because you meet the minimum criteria to be a part of this study and have expressed interest to me or my research supervisor, Julie Brice.

This interview will last anywhere between 30-60 minutes. You have the right to skip any question or stop the interview at any time. The audio of this interview will be recorded, and a transcription will be sent for your approval after the interview. Once the transcription is sent, you will have two weeks to review and suggest any changes you would like to make to the transcription or to pull out of the study.

Go over the Informed Consent Form

Audio Record

Questions

Introduction and Background

1. To the extent you are comfortable, what is your relationship to your gender identity and/or gender expression?
 - a. Is there a label you feel most connected to?
 - b. How comfortable are you expressing your gender identity in the spaces you consistently occupy?
 - c. To the extent you are comfortable, how do your other identities influence your relationship to your gender identity and/or expression?
2. What are your prior experiences with physical activity?
3. How long have you been participating in Zumba?
 - a. Approximately how many classes or length of time

- b. Did you have any preconceived notions about Zumba before going into your first class?

First Zumba Class

- 4. Can you tell me about your experience the first time you went to a Zumba class?
 - a. Why did you go? Were you with friends or family? Or did you go by yourself?
 - b. What were you feeling when you walked into the studio?
 - i. Were you able to find a spot in the studio easily?
 - ii. What types of people were in the class? Did you feel like anyone looked or acted like you?
 - c. Did it feel like everyone knew each other? Anyone reach out to talk to you?
- 5. What were some of your thoughts about the actual class?
 - a. Did the instructor give a spiel welcoming the class and giving the rundown about how the class is set up?
 - b. How were the dances?
 - i. I know you were probably trying to figure out the steps, but did the dances feel overly feminine or overly masculine? Overtly sexy?
 - c. Were there any moves or dances that made you feel uncomfortable or that you enjoyed?
 - i. Why?
- 6. How did you interact with other participants in the class?
 - a. Did anyone try dancing with you?
 - b. Were people clapping and high-fiving in between songs?
- 7. How did you feel after class was over?
 - a. Did anyone come up and talk to you?
- 8. For those who stayed, how did the class evolve over time?
 - a. Did your relationship with the dances change? How?
 - b. Did your relationships with the people change? How?

Decision to Stay or Go

- 9. Did you decide to continue going to classes or stop after the first one? Why?
 - a. For those that stopped going later on, why?
 - b. Did your gender identity play a part?
- 10. How has your relationship with your gender identity changed since participating in Zumba?
 - a. Were you given space to express yourself through the dances?
 - b. Did you face any internal or external barriers during participation?
- 11. Can you tell me about the Zumba community?
 - a. Do you feel connected to a Zumba community? Why?

12. In your experience, do you feel like Zumba promotes a gender-inclusive fitness space?
Why?
 - a. In your class, what tactics contributed to the consciousness (or lack thereof) of gender during the class?
 - i. Was there anything the Zumba instructor or other participants did or said that made you feel included or uncomfortable?
13. If you were to create your own Zumba class, what would you do? How would you cultivate community? What kind of dances and music would you use?